

The Effect of Job Satisfaction and Job Stress on Employee Performance (Study at PT. POS Indonesia Bangkalan Branch)

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ABSTRACT

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The aim of this study is to determine the effects of work stress and job satisfaction on employee performance at the PT POS Indonesia Bangkalan Branch. In this study, fifty employees of PT POS Indonesia's Bangkalan Branch participated as respondents. The basic data used in this study came from questionnaires that were distributed. The technique used is partial least square data analysis (PLS). The results of this study demonstrate that, although job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect, employee performance has a minor impact on workers' performance at the PT POS Indonesia Bangkalan branch.

KEYWORDS:

Job Satisfaction, Job Stress, Employee Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Globalization results in dynamic changes, especially for an employee who must master and keep up with technological developments, if employees cannot immediately adjust, it will have an impact on their performance. As an employee, of course, performance is the benchmark for assessment for a company. In addition, employee performance is very important for a company because it is one of the measuring instruments for increasing the company's success in achieving goals so that it can be said that the more employee performance increases, the better the company's performance.

The degree to which an employee is able to carry out his tasks at work is defined as employee performance by Nurdin and Djuhartono (2021). In light of this, the company's primary responsibility is to monitor employee performance, as a decline in it will directly affect the company's ability to survive and achieve its objectives. Job happiness is only one of the many elements that might lead to weakening or declining performance among employees.

Work stress is a situation that presses on a person's self or soul beyond his limits and long-term risks if left unchecked will affect a person's psychological health, (Fahmi, 2013: 256). If an employee experiences work stress, it will directly affect the work results and productivity levels, but on the other hand work stress is a natural condition experienced by

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every human being as a form of response to the extent of a person's ability to accept pressure or burden.

Response to the extent of a person's ability to accept the pressure or burden they feel. The bad impact if the stress felt is excessive can disrupt psychological instability which will have an impact on performance.

PT Pos Indonesia Persero is one of the state-owned companies engaged in postal services, one of which is in Bangkalan district. Increasingly, employees who are trusted by the company are someone who is capable and competent in their field so that it becomes an important task for the leadership to improve or maintain the level of employee performance and job satisfaction, besides that company leaders must give tasks and responsibilities according to the abilities of employees to avoid work stress. The following is a table of the number of package shipments that have problems or obstacles during delivery by PT POS Indonesia Bangkalan Branch.

Table 1. Delay in 2022 Package Delivery

Month	The number of packages that are blocked
January	98
February	77
March	116
April	64
May	76
June	100
July	89
August	91
September	81
October	125
November	75
December	322

Source: PT Pos Indonesia Bangkalan Branch delivery data

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Based on the table data above, it can be seen that in 2022 from January to December PT Pos Indonesia Bangkalan Branch there were several obstacles to sending packages, some of which were caused by unknown recipients, delays in sending packages, damaged package constraints, lost packages, no recipients and inappropriate addresses. In January to December, package delivery constraints fluctuate due to these obstacles occurring accidentally and naturally, the management of PT Pos Indonesia always strives to provide the best service for its customers in order to minimize unwanted events, so that consumers can trust the quality of service of PT Pos Indonesia Bangkalan Branch.

Table 2. PT. Employee Absenteeism Rate. Pos Indonesia Bangkalan branch.

Years	Number of employees	Sick	Permission	Alpha	Number of Employees Absent	Percentage (%)
2020	50	3	2	4	9	25.00 %
2021	50	5	5	8	18	50.00 %
2022	50	9	7	11	27	75.00 %

Source: Secondary Data

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the absenteeism of employees who do not enter work at PT Pos Indonesia is increasing every year, which means that further evaluation needs to be carried out by the company to find out the factors that affect employee performance so that it no longer has an impact on increasing the absenteeism of employees who do not enter or the absence of employees during the workday. Based on information obtained through a brief interview with the head of PT Pos Indonesia, Bangkalan branch, the researcher obtained information that employees are not fully satisfied with their work, because the work done is monotonous, causing boredom. Each employee has an excessive workload that makes employees exhausted. The criteria for employee performance appraisal are not clearly communicated so that it can create a negative impression on employees. Differences in opinion from previous research can be used as a basis for research, according to Wicaksana (2020) and Hutasuhut (2022) state that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance while research according to Annisa (2017) states that job satisfaction has an insignificant effect on employee performance.

Another problem that can cause an increase in the absenteeism rate of employees is derived from the level of work stress felt by employees such as workloads that are too heavy and some employees who work with demands for work deadlines with a specified time limit. The existence of workloads and deadlines can indicate stress. Differences in opinion from previous research can be used as a basis for research, according to Alfattama (2019) and Filliantoni et al

(2019) assert that employee performance is significantly impacted by job stress, however Bariroh (2017) asserts that employee performance is hardly impacted by work stress.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Job Satisfaction

According to Robbins (2015: 170), job satisfaction may be defined as the overall attitude that an employee has toward their work and the discrepancy between the many benefits they get and the numerous benefits they feel they should receive. In the meanwhile, job satisfaction is defined by Mangkunegara (2017: 117) as the joy that employees have while doing and seeing their work; if an individual is content with their job, then they are pleased with it. One of the most significant things that people have at work is job satisfaction. Job satisfaction, according to Hasibuan (2015: 202), is an emotional attitude that workers display because they like and are passionate about their work.

Job Stress

According to Robbins (2013), stress is a situation characterized by uncertainty and importance, whereby a person encounters opportunities, demands, or resources that align with their aspirations, but whose outcomes are not quite known. Work stress, according to Mangkunegara (2017: 157), is a situation in which workers experience pressure to complete tasks. An individual may have unstable emotions, excessive anxiety, tension, nervousness, and other problems as a result of job stress. Employers often encounter passive reactions from their staff, including tedium or boredom, exhaustion, burnout, helplessness, despair, lack of enthusiasm, and depressed mood (Kaswan, 2015: 247).

Employee Performance

As to Cashmere's (2016: 182) assertion, an individual's performance is the outcome of their labor and work behavior, which they attain by doing assigned duties and obligations within a certain time frame. The means by which an individual proves his capacity to execute duties that have been assigned to him and to which he has power is via performance. Consequently, Sodikin (2017: 130) defines performance as a purposeful, all-encompassing, and integrated process that involves performing regular reviews and assessments of each person's performance. As a business strives to accomplish its objectives, performance management helps it succeed by fostering the growth of HR performance.

Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance

When compared to workers who are not satisfied with their jobs, employees who are satisfied with their jobs produce better output. As a result, creating a positive work atmosphere is crucial for job happiness. Work satisfaction has a significant impact on employee performance because happy employees are more likely to feel that their goals have been

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met and that their work is a good fit for their expertise, which will enhance their performance while employed by a company.

H1 : Employee performance is significantly impacted by job satisfaction.

Job Stress and Employee Performance

Because workers do not have difficulties and may look bored due to understimulation, there is a significant correlation between workplace stress and employee performance. This association is particularly evident when employee stress levels are low. An ideal degree of stress will generate a range of creative ideas in a work, in addition to a rise in tension that may result in high performance. However, a high degree of stress will also have a negative impact on employee performance since the worker will feel under pressure from his task to the point where he is unable to finish it (Wartono, 2017).

H2 : Employee performance is significantly impacted by job stress.

Fig 1. Conceptual Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODS

In this research, employee performance is the independent variable, while work happiness and job stress are the independent variables. The study's population consists of 50 individuals who work at the PT Pos Indonesia Bangkalan branch. The full study population was included in the sample for this investigation. PLS software is used as part of the data analysis method in this study.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The subjects who were used as respondents in this study were employees who had employee status at PT POS Indonesia Bangkalan Branch, namely 50 people. The general description of the research subjects is carried out by describing the characteristics of respondents which include gender, education, age, and length of work which can be described as follows: (1) Most of the respondents were male as many as 28 people, (2) most of the respondents had undergraduate education, (3) most of the respondents in this study were 22-25 years old, (4) most of the respondents in this study had worked for 3-4 years, namely 17 people

Validity and Reability Test

Table 3. Avarage Extracted (AVE) and Composite Reliability

Variable	AVE	Composite reliability
Job satisfaction (X1)	0,737	0,933
Employee performance (Y)	0,659	0,906
Job Stress (X2)	0,925	0,984

Source: Data Processed 2024

It is feasible to conclude that the variables in this research already have exceptional validity values since convergent AVE values larger than 0.5 indicate that variables have sufficiently excellent validity values. The variables employed in this study had AVE values that are already greater than 0.5. The employee performance variable has a value of 0.933, the work stress variable has a value of 0.906, and the job satisfaction variable has a value of 0.984 according to the findings of the Composite Reliability testing. We may infer that the third variable is reliable since it displays a value greater than 0.70.

Fig .2 T-Statistic Bootstrapping

Source : Data Processed 2024

The PLS output image above shows the magnitude of the path coefficient, which is located above the arrow connecting the exogenous variable and the endogenous variable, and the magnitude of each indicator's factor loading value, which is located above the arrow connecting the variable and the indicator. Furthermore, it is possible to see the portion of the employee performance variable, or R-Square, that is included in the endogenous variable circle.

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Table 4. Path Coefficients (Mean, STDEV, T-Values, PValues)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0,696	0,708	0,073	9,564	0,000
Job Stress -> Employee Performance	-0,079	-0,082	0,102	0,781	0,435

Source: Data Processed 2024

It is clear that the association between work stress and employee performance as well as the link between job satisfaction qualities and employee performance have p-values less than 0.05. Thus, it may be said that whereas workplace stress has no discernible impact on employee performance, job happiness has a considerable impact on output.

IV. DISCUSSION

Effect of Job Satisfaction (X1) on Employee Performance (Y)

Because work satisfaction has a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be inferred from the study findings that job satisfaction has a substantial impact on employee performance. It makes sense that happier workers will perform better at work since they believe that their job satisfaction is a prerequisite for their ability to perform on a regular basis and that their work is a reflection of their individual areas of expertise.

The presence of promotions based on achievement is the measure of job satisfaction that has the biggest impact on performance. This way, employees will feel satisfied when the company chooses their career paths because of their accomplishments. Additionally important to the development of a positive work environment is job satisfaction. There is a strong relationship between worker performance and job happiness. Happy workers are more likely to be enthusiastic about their jobs as they are in line with their areas of competence and will boost productivity for the organization.

The results of this research are in line with those of Hutasuhut (2022) and Wicaksana (2020) investigations, which demonstrate that employee performance is strongly impacted by job satisfaction. This, however, runs counter to a 2017 research by Annisa, which found that job satisfaction had no effect on employee performance..

Effect of work stress (X2) on employee performance (Y)

As a consequence of the study findings, it is possible to draw the conclusion that job stress has no discernible influence on employee performance, with a p-value of $0.435 < 0.05$. That not all stress is bad, as Sofyan (2019) explains. Because minor stress will, at some point, have a good impact or increase workers' performance—in other words, it will motivate or push employees to accomplish duties better—

management should not be concerned if their staff feel it. It is possible to induce mild stress in workers in order to boost productivity and critical thinking. When faced with challenges, the brain is more likely to search for ways to find a quick solution to the task at hand.

Based on the study's findings, staff members at the Bangkalan branch of PT POS Indonesia believe that their performance at work is unaffected by work-related stress because their workload at the POS office requires accuracy when entering data for delivery or payment in order to minimize recording errors. They also believe that working under such demanding conditions is normal for their position. Employee responses indicating that work stress is normal based on the points provided are negatively correlated with the researcher's conclusion that employee job stress is very high. Due to the fact that work stress is actually commonplace and has no effect on employees, employee performance is also high under the current circumstances. This is because employee performance is excellent because it aligns with the agency's values, which call for always performing excellently given the task load received.

The findings of this investigation are consistent with those of Bariroh's (2017) study, which found no discernible impact of job stress on worker performance. However, this is at odds with study by Alfattama (2019), which finds that employee performance is significantly impacted by job stress.

V. CONCLUSION

On the basis of the findings of the investigation carried out, it can be concluded that:

1. Employee performance at PT POS Indonesia Bangkalan Branch is influenced by job satisfaction. If workers are happy with their jobs and what they have accomplished, they will be motivated to work harder for the company because their jobs fit their skills and enhance their performance.
2. Employee performance at the Bangkalan Branch of PT POS Indonesia is unaffected by work-related stress; rather, a certain amount of stress might enhance performance by motivating staff to carry out their functions more effectively.

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